

EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF ONYCHOMYCOSIS AND STUDYING THE INFLUENCE OF THE DURATION OF THE PATHOLOGICAL PROCESS ON THE PREVALENCE

Baratova Mavjuda Raximovna

Samarkand State Medical University Department of Skin
and Venereal Diseases

Abstract: this article attempts to reveal the main reasons for the influence of the duration of autoimmune pathology on the effectiveness of the treatment of onychomycosis of the feet. To carry out scientific work, the author observed 150 patients in the rheumatology department of the Altai Regional Clinical Hospital aged 18 to 70 years with autoimmune pathology and onychomycosis of the feet. The control group included 115 patients with onychomycosis of the feet without concomitant somatic diseases, examined and treated in the consultative and diagnostic department. The problem in question is still little studied, therefore, requires more thorough research.

Key words: Onychomycosis, treatment efficiency.

Introduction: Onychomycosis (from the Greek *ónyx* - nail and *mýkēs* - fungus) is a fungal infection of the nail. It is caused, as a rule, by dermatophyte fungi *Trichophyton rubrum*, *Trichophyton interdigitale*, *Trichophyton tonsurans*, less often *Epidermophyton floccosum* and microsporia (*Microsporum canis*) and others.

There are three types of onychomycosis (underlying the Russian classification):

- normotrophic - the color of the nail changes, stripes and spots appear, but the luster and thickness of the nail remain normal;
- hypertrophic - the color of the nail changes, it loses its luster, thickens and deforms. Perhaps partial destruction of the nail from the edges;
- onycholytic (atrophic) - the affected part of the nail atrophies and is torn away

from the nail bed.

By localization, forms of onychomycosis are distinguished (used for classification by foreign doctors):

- distal (damage to the nail at the free edge);
- lateral (damage to the sides);
- proximal (damage to the posterior ridge);
- total (damage to the entire nail).

When diagnosing, one should distinguish between onychomycosis and non-fungal nail deformities (their occurrence approximately coincides). For accurate diagnosis, laboratory tests are used.

The cause of onychomycosis is often associated with the peculiarities of the profession and improper care of the legs:

- poor foot and nail care, lack of daily hygiene procedures due to neglect of personal hygiene rules or difficulties in their implementation (in bedridden patients or patients with limited mobility);
- work in wet, damp areas (greenhouses, greenhouses, vegetable stores), frequent wearing of rubber gloves or rubber shoes;
- professional sports activities;
- wearing uncomfortable, tight, narrow shoes or shoes made of artificial materials (leatherette), creating a "greenhouse effect" that prevents normal air exchange.

In women, a common cause of the fungus is long-term wearing of gel polish. It creates a closed space between the nail plate and the coating, in which a fungal infection successfully develops.

Aim: to study the effect of the duration of autoimmune pathology on the effectiveness of the treatment of onychomycosis of the feet.

Materials and methods: 150 patients of the rheumatology department of the Altai Regional Clinical Hospital aged 18 to 70 years with autoimmune pathology and onychomycosis of the feet were under observation. The control group

included 115 patients with onychomycosis of the feet without concomitant somatic diseases, examined and treated in the consultative and diagnostic department of the Regional Dermatovenerologic Dispensary. To make a diagnosis of onychomycosis of the feet, a mycological examination was carried out, which included two stages - microscopy and cultural diagnostics. If indicated, systemic antifungal drugs were prescribed. All patients underwent mechanical cleaning of the nail plates, followed by treatment with antifungal varnish.

Results: in patients of the rheumatological group and the severity of onychomycosis of the feet, which required the appointment of systemic antimycotics, the results of complete recovery by the 72nd week of observation had no significant differences depending on the duration of the underlying disease and ranged from $53.33 \pm 14.98\%$ to $68.42 \pm 12.4\%$. In patients with mild fungal infection of the nail plates of the feet, who received only external treatment, with the duration of the concomitant autoimmune process up to 5 years, complete recovery was observed in all treated patients, with the duration of the concomitant pathology from 5 to 10 years - $77.78 \pm 16, 12\%$, with a duration of more than 10 years in the absence of systemic therapy, a complete recovery did not occur in any patient. In patients of the control group, complete recovery with the use of systemic antimycotics was achieved in $79.22 \pm 7.6\%$ of patients, against the background of external therapy - in $60.53 \pm 13.04\%$ of those treated.

Conclusions: the effectiveness of the treatment of onychomycosis of the feet in rheumatological patients using systemic antifungal drugs is lower than in persons without concomitant diseases and does not significantly depend on the duration of the underlying disease; external antifungal monotherapy is not effective in patients with a duration of concomitant autoimmune pathology for more than 10 years

Literature:

1. Тошев С. У., Сулаймонов А. Л., Тиллакобиллов И. Б. ТЕРАПИЯ ВИТИЛИГО С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ ПОЛИОКСИДОНИЯ В СОЧЕТАНИИ С ЛЮКОДЕРМИНОМ //Высшая школа: научные исследования. – 2019. – С. 55-

59.

2. Тошев С. У., Аширов З. Ф., Абдуллаев Х. Д. ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ВИТИЛИГО 308-нм ЭКСИМЕРНЫМ ЛАЗЕРОМ //Актуальные аспекты медицинской деятельности. – 2021. – С. 240-243.
3. Salamova L. A. et al. Evaluation of the effectiveness of the drug gepon in the treatment of genital condylomas. – 2021.
4. Davlatovich A. X. VAGINAL TRIXOMONADLAR SHITAMMASINI TRIXOPOLGA VA XIMOTRIPSIN BILAN BILAN SEZGICHLIGINI ANIQLASH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 645-647.
5. Davlatovich A. X., Orifovich S. D., Baxtiyorovich A. S. Studying the Relationship of Local Immune Status and the Course of Burn Disease //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 679-682.
6. Xolmurodovich D. J., Umidovich N. T., Davlatovich A. X. CLINIC COURSE OF NONSPECIFIC PNEUMONIA //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 510-513.
7. Абдуллаев Х. Д. и др. ЛАЗЕР В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ВИТИЛИГО //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 495-500.
8. Hikmatovich I. N. et al. The use of Fungite in the Local Treatment of Genital Herpes //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 231-232.
9. Davlatovich A. X., O'gli A. B. X., O'gli I. A. S. BOLALARDA GENITAL GERPESNI DAVOLASH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 367-369.
10. Xolmurodovich D. J., Orifovich R. S., Davlatovich A. X. FEATURES OF THE MICROELEMENT STATUS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS IN CHILDREN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 447-450.

11. Davlatovich A. X. DETERMINATION OF GENE ACTIVITY IN VITILIGO PATIENTS //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 451-454.
12. Davlatovich A. X. et al. EVALUATION OF THE GENERAL SOMATIC STATUS OF PATIENTS WITH VITILIGO BASED ON THE DETERMINATION OF THE CONTENT OF NATURAL ANTIBODIES TO VARIOUS ORGANIS AND TISSUES OF THE BODY //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 472-476.
13. Davlatovich A. X. et al. USING IMMUNOMAX AND 0.1% TACROLIMUS OINTMENT IN THE TREATMENT OF VITILIGO //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 559-562.
14. Абдуллаев Х., Толибов М. Allergodermatozlar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan vulgar acneni kompleks davolash Samaraligini o'rganish //Журнал гепатогастроэнтерологических исследований. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.2. – С. 73-74.
15. Ахмедов Ш. К. и др. ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ИЗОТРЕТИНОИНА ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ УГРЕВОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ //Академический журнал Западной Сибири. – 2015. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 56-56.
16. Нуруллаева А. А., Рахматова А. Х., Абдуллаев Х. Д. ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МИКРОБНОГО ОБСЕМЕНЕНИЯ КОЖИ ПРИ НЕКОТОРЫХ ЗУДЯЩИХ ДЕРМАТОЗАХ //Молодежь и медицинская наука в XXI веке. – 2019. – С. 125-125.
17. Абдуллаев Х. Д., Собиров М. С., Жумаева Д. Х. НЕРВНО-ПСИХИЧЕСКИЙ СТАТУС У БОЛЬНЫХ СЕБОРЕЕЙ //Молодежь и медицинская наука в XXI веке. – 2018. – С. 115-116.
18. Iskandarovna K. M. SIFILISNING IMMUNOASSAY SHAKLLARI //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 534-536.

19. Iskandarovna K. M., Dilshodovna A. D., Adxamovna A. A. Impact of Socio-Hygienic Conditions of Life on the Health of Students //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 644-646.
20. Iskandarovna K. M. et al. Comprehensive Assessment of the Levels of Somatic Health and Disturbances of Adaptation Reserves in Medical Students //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 641-643.
21. Iskandarovna K. M., Alamovich K. A., Rabbimovich N. A. Treatment of Urethrogenic Prostatitis Associated with Chlamydia Infection //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 44-46.
22. Iskandarovna K. M., Buribaevna I. S., Azamovna A. N. Immunoassay Forms of Syphilis //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 47-49.
23. Ахмедова М. М., Абдуллаев Х. Д., Камолова М. И. ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ОНИХОМИКОЗОВ У ВЗРОСЛЫХ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 186-190.
24. Абдуллаев Д. М., Абдуллаев Х. Д., Камолова М. И. ОПЫТ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ КРЕМАТЕРБИЗИЛ ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ МИКОЗОВ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 181-185.
25. Teshaboeva K., Israilova S., Qurbonov A. PREVENTION MEASURES FOR MAJOR NON-EPIDEMIC DISEASES //МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ. – 2021. – С. 97-99.